

A Novel and Facile Synthesis of Barbatusol Methyl Ether

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The rearranged 9(10 → 20)-abeo-abietane skeleton, a rare structural type of diterpene thought to arise from rearrangement of the more familiar abietane skeleton¹, has received considerable attention in the last few years. Several new members of this group have been isolated², and the total or partial syntheses of some of them have been reported³. Among them barbatusol (**1a**) was isolated from the source as the pharmacologically potent diterpene forskolin^{3a}, and was found to induce bradycardia and lowering of blood pressure in mice. Although its total synthesis has been reported^{3a,3e}, as a part of our synthetic studies on the naturally occurring diterpenes, we wanted to develop a more simple and effective synthetic route to this type of diterpenes. Herein we report a novel and facile convergent synthesis of barbatusol methyl ether, a key intermediate to barbatusol, featuring a selective reduction of phenylethene with Li/NH₃(l)⁴, and a selective oxidation of allyl methyl group with selenium dioxide⁵.

Scheme 1

Our synthetic strategy, derived from the retrosynthetic analysis (Scheme 1), was outlined in Scheme 2. 3,4-Dimethoxybenzyltriphenylphosphonium bromide (**4**), readily available from 3,4-dimethoxybenzaldehyde (**5**) by standard reduction with sodium borohydride, bromination with phosphorus tribromide and then reaction with triphenylphosphine in a overall

yield of 81.2% coupled with racemic α -cyclocitral (**3**)⁶ led to the formation of **6**. The selective hydrogenation of phenylethene in the presence of 10% Pd-C^{3b} was reported, but our experimental results showed it to be ineffective. We assumed that 10% Pd-C was not acting well, so we selectively reduced **6** with lithium-liquid ammonia to give **7** in 83.1% yield.

Selective oxidation of **7** with selenium dioxide furnished the desired alcohol (**8**) in a yield of 64.2%.

Scheme 2. Reagents : (i) a) NaBH₄, CH₃OH, R T (94.6%), b) PBr₃, petroleum ether, R T (92.5%), c) PPh₃, benzene, reflux (92.8%); (ii) BuLi, then α -cyclocitral (83.1%); (iii) Li-NH₃(l) (88%); (iv) Bu^tO₂H, SeO₂ (64.2%); (v) PPA, 18–22° (60.7%); (vi) BuLi, then acetone (91.4%); (vii) LiAlH₄-Cp₂TiCl₂ (57.1%).

In order to avoid the migration of ethylene bond, the intramolecular cyclisation was conducted at room temperature and the reaction mixture was quickly quenched as the reaction was complete. The desired compound **9** was obtained in 60.7% yield, along with a trace of **10**.

Compound **11** was readily available from **9** by lithiation with butyllithium, followed by addition of acetone in 91.4% yield⁷. Hydrogenolysis of **11** by lithium aluminium hydride in the presence of dicyclopentadienyl titanium dichloride led to the corresponding deoxygenated product **1b**⁸. Because demethylation of **1b** was reported by Koft^{3a} and Majetich *et al.*³⁰ who achieved a formal synthesis of **1a**, we did not further convert **1b** to **1a**. The overall yield for the synthesis of **1b** from **5** was 12.7%.

Experimental

Ir spectra were recorded on a FT-170SX spectrophotometer. The spectra of solid samples were run as KBr discs, while those of liquid and semisolid were run as thin films on KBr plate. Nmr spectra (CDCl₃) were recorded on a Bruker Am-400 instrument with TMS as the internal standard and mass spectra on a ZAB-MS spectrometer.

3-(3,4-Dimethoxyphenylethenyl)-2,4,4-trimethyl-1-cyclohexene (6) : Under nitrogen, 3,4-dimethoxybenzyltriphenylphosphoniumbromide (14 g, 29.3 mmol) was dissolved in anhydrous benzene (150 ml), and then a solution of butyllithium (1.5 M; 20 ml) in ether was added slowly at 0°. The mixture was stirred at 0° for 1.5 h and a solution of racemic α -cyclocitral (4.6 g, 30.2 mmol) in dry benzene (5 ml) was added slowly at 0°. After stirring at this temperature for 1 h and then at room temperature for 5 h, the mixture was poured into ice-dilute HCl and extracted with ether. The standard ethereal workup and purification by FCG gave **6** (6.7 g, 83%); (*m/z*) 286 (25), 272 (5), 163 (100); δ 6.98–6.48 (3H, m), 6.40–6.00 (2H, m), 5.32 (1H, m), 3.88 (3H, s), 3.86 (3H, s), 3.82 (1H, m), 2.14 (2H, m), 1.86 (3H, m), 1.47 (2H, m), 0.99 (3H, s), 0.95 (3H, s); ν_{\max} 3 603, 3 109, 2 948, 2 860, 1 590, 1 518, 1 382, 1 363 cm⁻¹.

3-(3,4-Dimethoxyphenethyl)-2,4,4-trimethyl-1-cyclohexene (7) : A solution of **6** (5.72 g, 20 mmol) in anhydrous ether (4 ml) was added to distilled liquid ammonia (100 ml), then lithium pieces (0.28 g, 40 mmol) was added slowly, and the mixture was stirred for 2 h. After the ammonia was evaporated, a solution of saturated NH₄Cl (30 ml) was added and extracted with ether. The standard ethereal workup and purification by FCG gave **7** (5.03 g, 88%); (*m/z*) 288 (13), 274 (2), 177 (10), 165 (13), 164 (85), 152 (28), 151 (100), 137 (15), 107 (12); δ 6.96 (1H, s), 6.62–6.38 (2H, dd), 5.42 (1H, m), 3.92 (3H, s), 3.88 (3H, s), 2.65 (2H, t, *J* 7.9 Hz), 2.40 (1H, m), 2.06 (2H, m), 1.86 (3H, s), 1.74–1.48 (4H, m), 0.98 (3H, s), 0.81 (3H, s); ν_{\max} 3 432, 2 951, 2 931, 2 867, 1 590, 1 514, 1 463, 1 382, 1 363, 1 335, 1 261 cm⁻¹.

3-(3,4-Dimethoxyphenethyl)-4,4-dimethyl-2-hydroxymethyl-1-cyclohexene (8) : To a stirred solution of selenium dioxide (811 mg, 8 mmol) and 75% t-butylhydroperoxide (3.6 ml, 29.8 mmol) in dichloromethane (23 ml) was added dropwise a solution of **7** (4.3 g, 15 mmol) in dichloromethane (10 ml) at room temperature. The mixture was stirred for 6 h, diluted with ether (30 ml), washed with water (15 ml) and brine (15 ml), and dried over sodium sulphate. After the solvent was removed in vacuum, the residue was dissolved in methanol (23 ml), to which was added sodium borohydride (450 mg, 11.5 mmol) portionwise at 0° with stirring. After being stirred for 45 min, the solvent was removed under reduced pressure. The resulting residue was dissolved in ether (100 ml), washed with 2 N HCl (10 ml) and water (10 ml), then dried over sodium sulphate. Evaporation of the solvent gave a residue which was chromatographed on silica gel to give **8** (2.93 g, 64.2%); (*m/z*) 304 (5), 387 (11), 272 (8), 216 (4), 151 (50), 121 (100); δ 6.95 (1H, s), 6.62, 6.38 (2H, dd), 5.51 (1H, m), 4.30 (2H, s), 3.89, 3.87 (6H, ss), 2.62 (2H, t, *J* 8.1 Hz), 2.43 (1H, m), 2.10 (2H, m), 1.72–1.51 (4H, m), 0.95 (3H, s), 0.83 (3H, s); ν_{\max} 3 510, 3 432, 2 946, 2 862, 1 586, 1 526, 1 381, 1 358, 1 039 cm⁻¹.

13-Deisopropyl barbatusol methyl ether (9) : To **8** (3 g, 9.9 mmol) was added polyphosphoric acid (40 g) at room temperature and the mixture was stirred for 3 h. After cooling, ice-water (100 ml)

was added and then extracted with ethyl acetate (5 × 50 ml). The extract was washed with saturated sodium hydrocarbonate (2 × 30 ml), brine (2 × 30 ml) and dried over sodium sulphate. After evaporating the solvent, the residue was purified to give **9** (1.7 g, 60.7%); *m/z* 286 (39), 271 (31), 203 (32), 177 (24), 165 (46), 151 (100), 115 (60); δ 6.84 (1H, d, *J* 7.5 Hz), 6.68 (1H, d, *J* 7.5 Hz), 5.49 (1H t, *J* 8.1 Hz), 3.85 (3H, s), 3.83 (3H, s), 3.72 (1H, d, *J* 15.8 Hz), 2.99 (2H, d, *J* 15.8 Hz), 2.80 (2H, m), 2.51 (1H, m), 2.12 (2H, m), 1.79–1.18 (4H, m), 0.89 (3H, s), 0.82 (3H, s); ν_{\max} 2 929, 2 869, 1 607, 1 463, 1 360, 1 258, 1 098 cm^{-1} .

15-Hydroxybarbatusol methyl ether (11): A solution of **9** (1.5 g, 5.2 mmol) in anhydrous THF (20 ml) was stirred at room temperature and the solution of butyllithium (1.5 M; 4 ml) in ether was added dropwise for 10 min under nitrogen. After the mixture solution was stirred for another 2 h, a solution of acetone (0.35 g, 6 mmol) in anhydrous THF (3 ml) was added dropwise at -30° . The mixture was stirred for 1 h at -30° and for 2 h at room temperature then a solution of saturated ammonium chloride (15 ml) was added slowly. The standard ethereal workup and purification by FCG gave **11** (1.67 g, 91.4%); *m/z* 344 (20), 327 (9), 329 (100), 311 (12), 151 (67); δ 6.71 (1H, s), 5.50 (1H, t, *J* 8 Hz), 3.96 (3H, s), 3.86 (3H, s), 3.71 (1H, d, *J* 15.6 Hz), 3.01 (1H, d, *J* 15.6 Hz) 2.79 (2H, m), 2.49 (1H, m), 2.12 (2H, m), 1.79–1.21 (4H, m), 1.63 (6H, s), 0.88 (3H, m), 0.80 (3H, s); ν_{\max} 3 467, 3 069, 2 980, 2 833, 1 607, 1 520, 1 363, 1 265, 1 072 cm^{-1} .

Barbatusol methyl ether (1b): A mixture of **11** (1.5 g, 4.4 mmol), lithium aluminium hydride (1.02 g, 26.9 mmol) and dicyclopentadienyl titanium

dichloride (0.096 g, 0.4 mmol) in anhydrous THF (30 ml) was refluxed for 5 h. Then saturated ammonium chloride (25 ml) was added slowly at 0° and the mixture was extracted with ether (10 ml × 2). The standard ethereal workup and purification by FCG gave **1b** (845 mg, 57.1%); *m/z* 328 (M^{+} , 94), 285 (30), 270 (64), 193 (100), 165 (38), 141 (28); δ 6.69 (1H, s), 5.51 (1H, t, *J* 7.8 Hz), 3.86 (3H, s), 3.84 (3H, s), 3.74 (1H, d, *J* 16 Hz), 3.24 (1H, sept, *J* 7.1 Hz), 3.0 (1H, d, *J* 16 Hz), 2.82–2.66 (2H, m), 2.08–1.84 (3H, m), 1.83–1.72 (1H, m), 1.40–1.14 (3H, m), 1.17 (6H, dd, *J* 7 Hz), 0.89 (3H, s), 0.85 (3H, s); ν_{\max} 2 938, 1 440, 1 328, 1 296, 1 095, 1 045 cm^{-1} .

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